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Social Life Cycle Assessment in Construction: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

Urbanisation leads to the expansion of urban areas, which needs vigorous support from the construction sector for infrastructure development. While this sector is a contributor to job creation and economic development, it is also a major consumer of energy and greenhouse gas emissions, which emphasises its need for sustainable development. Achieving complete sustainable development involves an integration of social dimensions as well, which is often neglected in conventional Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). Despite the recent development of S-LCA guidelines, research output remains limited compared to traditional LCA. This study aims to analyse research trends, patterns, and impacts of the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) within the construction sector by reviewing available literature. To fulfil the objectives, a bibliometric analysis was conducted with the help of Scopus using the keywords - “Construction” and “S-LCA,” and network maps were generated using VOSviewer. Results imply that there is an increase in research from 2023-2024, denoting this to be a fast-emerging field. Though the research principally originated from the West, still there was an increasing contribution from the East, like China and Malaysia, which underlines the potential for collaboration between them. The focus on the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA), which covers economic, environmental, and social dimensions, highlights its importance for construction projects in the future. The study concludes that S-LCA is significant for understanding the overall impacts of construction projects on different stakeholders involved. More focus on S-LCA research can help in the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Keywords

Social Life Cycle Assessment, Bibliometric Analysis, Construction

1 Introduction

Urban areas contribute most of the greenhouse gases, accounting for 67–72% of the global emissions in 2020 (IPCC 2023). Urbanisation drives economic growth and infrastructure development, but it also leads to environmental and social problems. The construction industry is a major source of employment and is also a major contributor to pollution (Tabassum Ira 2021). In different life cycle stages, construction-related activities yield air, noise, and water pollution, impacting both the

environment and human health (Hong *et al.* 2020, Wieser *et al.* 2021). Furthermore, indoor spaces like walls and doors may release pollutants due to applied glues and paints, and pollutants are also released from the heating and ventilation of the buildings (Wieser *et al.* 2021), which can further exacerbate human health (Hong *et al.* 2020).

Traditionally, sustainability involves three dimensions – social, economic, and environmental, but the social dimension is often neglected (Khan 2020). While guidelines for S-LCA were first introduced in 2009 (UNEP 2009) and updated in 2020 (UNEP 2020), research in this field is less (Marta and Giulia 2020). Considering the above-mentioned concerns and gaps, this study aims to understand the research patterns, trends and impacts of S-LCA in the construction sector.

To achieve the objectives, a bibliometric analysis was conducted using Scopus as the primary data source, given its extensive indexing of peer-reviewed journals (Singh *et al.* 2021). The search query used specific keywords related to S-LCA and construction, from 2015 to November 2024. This period is chosen so that the focus is on the most recent research, which will help in consistency and comparability; also, this helps in managing the data in the limited time available. The retrieved literature was analysed with the help of VOSviewer. This research examined the geographical distribution of research, leading journals, key themes, and collaboration networks, which provided valuable information on the evolution of S-LCA in construction.

The documents found in this study, in the highest cited papers or in bibliographic coupling, can be used by other researchers for their study, thus making their search easier. This research is the first phase of a multi-stage study which is being conducted as part of the ProLight project. It will help in the understanding of S-LCA's role in sustainable urban development and its application on the construction site. Future research will expand beyond bibliometric analysis to conduct systematic literature reviews and case studies, ensuring a practical translation of S-LCA findings into demonstration sites. Though this research's scope is limited, it is an important step for future research. The overall research results will benefit different people like policymakers, researchers, construction professionals, and vulnerable social groups by encouraging more socially responsible and sustainable construction practices as S-LCA helps in understanding the impacts of the product or service on the stakeholders (UNEP 2020).

2 Literature Review

Cities are the major contributors to CO₂ emissions. Approximately 56% of people on the planet resided in cities in 2021, and this percentage is expected to rise to 68% by 2050 (Oginga Martins and Sharifi 2022). Cities use 60 to 80 % of the energy produced globally, and they also contribute nearly the same amount of CO₂ emissions to the atmosphere (Kamal-Chaoui and Robert 2009). Development needs more cities, which in turn need construction. The construction sector produces different kinds of problems like noise – which can be due to heavy machinery used in the construction site. Other forms of problems can be vibrations and dust, which may drastically affect the people working on the site and even the neighbours (Hong *et al.* 2020). In the review by Wieser *et al.* 2021, the authors focused on air pollution from the construction industry and observed that air pollution is a significant environmental concern here. The above information highlights the challenge that the construction industry poses for sustainability. To tackle this issue life cycle assessment is a viable way to help reduce the damages caused by the construction sector, and its integration into decision-making will be important for sustainable development (Wieser *et al.* 2021). To fulfil the goals of sustainable development for any project, it is important to accomplish all three dimensions - social, economic, and environmental, and many times the social part is neglected (Khan 2020).

According to ISO 14040:2006 (Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework), life cycle assessment (LCA) incorporates the entire life cycle of a product, initiating

with the extraction of the raw material and continuing through the production of energy and material, manufacturing, use, and ultimately, end-of-life treatment and disposal. LCA evaluates only the environmental effects of a product and neglects the economic and social impacts that are considered outside the boundary of LCA. Other tools can be used to evaluate the environmental and social effects of the product (ISO 2006). These other tools include life cycle costing and social life cycle assessment. The first guidelines for S-LCA were published in 2009 called “*Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products 2009*” followed by updated guidelines called “*Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020*”. Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) has emerged as a critical methodology for evaluating the social impacts of products and services which can be both positive and negative throughout their life cycle (UNEP 2009, 2020).

3 Research Methodology

This research uses bibliometric analysis, which helps in exploring the research field’s bibliometric and rational structure by doing analysis, like relations between different authors, countries, and keywords. It helps in narrowing down the research topics to have a trend and composition of the research (Passas 2024). This method gives an unbiased and total assessment of the research world (Baharudin et al. 2021), whereas standard literature reviews may be biased and sometimes restricted in scope (Tseng and Tsay 2013, Garcia and You 2016, Farrukh et al. 2020).

The methodology followed three important steps. The first step involved data collection, where the relevant literature was identified based on the search criteria used in *Scopus*. More than 99% of journals indexed in *Web of Science* are also indexed in *Scopus* (Singh et al. 2021), so *Scopus* was used to search the literature for this research. The keywords were “Social LCA” and “Construction” and the query used was (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("social life cycle assessment" OR "S-LCA" OR "Social LCA" OR "SLCA") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("construction" OR "construction sector")). To enhance the quality of the results, only publications from 2015 to November 2024 were considered, and only English literature was included. This period is chosen so that primarily the focus is on the most recent research which will help in consistency and comparability; also, this helps in managing the data in the limited time available to finish this research.

The second step involved data processing and network analysis, where the selected documents were analysed using VOSviewer (version 1.2.20). It was used to generate co-occurrence maps, citation networks, and collaboration clusters. VOSviewer is one of the best available free tools (Colina Vargas et al. 2022), so it is used in this research. It is a free software which was developed by Leiden University, Netherlands. It helps the researchers construct bibliometric maps related to co-citation, co-authorship and similar (Centre for Science and Technology Studies 2024). These maps help the researchers identify emerging trends and future research directions (Hsieh and Yeh 2024).

The last step is to interpret the results, which involved critically analysing the findings to conclude the evolution of S-LCA research in construction, highlighting dominant themes, geographical distribution, and influential studies.

Figure 1. Flowchart showing screening of literature

4 Findings and Discussion

The Scopus search yielded ninety-two publications (Figure 1). After filtering English-language publications, the results were reduced to ninety-one publications. Furthermore, when the Scopus search was restricted to publications from 2015 to 2024, the number of results was limited to eighty (Figure 1). These eighty publications were used in bibliometric analysis.

Figure 2. Annual number of publications

4.1 Analysis of the Total Literature

The overall trend of annual publications (Figure 2) indicates that there is a growing academic interest in the topic. Initially, between 2016-2017, there was a fluctuation in the total number of publications, but there was a notable increase between 2023 to 2024, with the highest publication at 20 in 2024. This highlights the possible recognition of S-LCA in sustainable construction. Rapid growth from 2023-2024 indicates an increase in academic interest and/or higher research investments (Ganz and Vincent 2022).

Figure 3. Division based on type of literature

Of the 80 publications (Figure 3), the majority were articles (65%), which indicates a strong reliance on peer-reviewed literature and states the well-establishment of the research path. Followed by reviews (16%), book chapters and conference papers (9% each), with only 1% being conference reviews.

4.2 Analysis of Literature by Countries

The geographical distribution of the research stipulates that most of the literature (Table 1) is published in Italy and Spain, with 10 each, followed by China and Germany, with 9 each. The United States has 8 publications, followed by Australia, and Malaysia, with 7 each. Many countries have only a single publication. Most publication hotspots (Table 1) are in the developed nations, which is primarily Europe and North America, as well as there are some emerging contributions from China and Malaysia, which indicates an increase in global interest in this field.

Table 1 Geographical distribution of literature

Country	Publications	Country	Publications	Country	Publications
Italy	10	Brazil	2	Indonesia	1
Spain	10	France	2	Japan	1
China	9	India	2	Norway	1
Germany	9	Iran	2	Pakistan	1
United States	8	Netherlands	2	Qatar	1
Australia	7	Singapore	2	Russian Federation	1
Malaysia	7	Sweden	2	South Africa	1
United Kingdom	7	Vietnam	2	Sri Lanka	1
Canada	6	Austria	1	Thailand	1
Hong Kong	4	Colombia	1	Turkey	1
Belgium	3	Croatia	1	Undefined	1
Denmark	3	Greece	1		
Portugal	3	Hungary	1		

The co-authorship analysis is an effective way of understanding the relationship between countries. This network is a social network in which the authors, through participation in one or more publications through an indirect path have links with each other. The links are the number of their common writings which are connected by a line (Fonseca *et al.* 2016).

The first cluster is blue, with China and Canada, having the link strength of just one, this indicates bilateral research between

Figure 4. Co-authorship in countries (with a minimum of 5 documents per country)

them (Figure 4). The second cluster is green, which comprises three European countries – Germany, Italy and Spain, indicating strong European research partnerships (Figure 4). The last cluster is red, which comprises the United States, Australia, Malaysia and the United Kingdom, with a strong connection between Malaysia and the UK, compared to other connections in this group(Figure 4).

It is essential to recognise the existence of a strong collaboration between Western nations (US, UK, Australia) with regional cooperation in Europe between Italy, Spain, and Germany, while there are also emerging players (China, Malaysia and Canada) who have room for amalgamation in the broader global networks. This will help with enhancing knowledge transfer and enhancing social sustainability globally.

4.3 Analysis of Literature by Sources

The third component generated from the bibliometric study is the main sources of literature. Table 2 lists the sources with at least two publications. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment (Springer)* leads with 15 out of the 80 publications, which indicates the central role of this journal in this field, with 4 articles each in 2021 and 2024. Followed by *Sustainability Switzerland (MDPI)*, which accounts for 9 publications, it is publishing consistently from 2021-2024. This is followed by *Journal of Cleaner Production (Elsevier)* and *Sustainable Production and Consumption (Elsevier)*, with 4 articles each. These four journals are major contributors to this research field.

The Cite Score analysis indicates that *Journal of Cleaner Production (Elsevier)* has a score of 20.4 and has 4 documents, making it the most influential journal. Cite Score is considered an indicator of high relevance in a source(Escorcía Hernández *et al.* 2023), so this journal can be a reliable source for similar articles in future, as well as it is a good place to publish articles on the current researched topic. While *IOP Conference Series Earth and Environmental Science* and *Environmental Footprints and Eco Design of Products and Processes* have lower Cite Scores, which suggests their less influence on the academia. Overall, this stresses the need to emphasise the importance of targeting high-visibility channels to enhance academic and policy influence.

Table 2 Journals with the highest publications

S No	Journal	Publications	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Cite Score	SJR
1	International Journal Of Life Cycle Assessment	15	2	1	0	2	0	1	4	0	1	4	10.6	1.203
2	Sustainability Switzerland	9	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	4	1	6.8	0.672
3	Journal Of Cleaner Production	4	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	1	20.4	2.058
4	Sustainable Production And Consumption	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	17.4	2.359
5	Building And Environment	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	12.5	1.647
6	Buildings	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	3.4	0.575
7	Environment Development And Sustainability	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	10.2	0.889
8	Environmental Footprints And Eco Design Of Products And Processes	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1.2	0.133
9	Environmental Impact Assessment Review	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	12.6	1.963
10	Iop Conference Series Earth And Environmental Science	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	0.199
11	Journal Of Building Engineering	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	10	1.397
12	Resources	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	7.2	0.699
13	Sustainable Cities And Society	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	22	2.545

4.4 Analysis of Top-Cited Articles

This analysis highlights the most influential contributions and authors in the field. The article by *Zheng et al. 2019* has the highest number of citations (112), followed by *Dong and Ng 2015* with 100 citations and *Larsen et al. 2022* with 93 citations (Table 3). It is fascinating to know that these publications are

not very old and still have plenty of citations. Furthermore, seven of the top ten publications are centred on life cycle sustainability analysis (LCSA), indicating a strong focus on the integration of environmental, economic, and social dimensions. Also, this suggests that their methodology and approach are widely referenced, implying that they are the best choices for further S-LCA-related research. The *Journal of Cleaner Production (Elsevier)* and *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment (Springer)* emerged as key publication players, strengthening them as a venue for high-impact S-LCA research. The dominance is of the methodology-focused and case-study-based studies in the top-cited papers. Fifteen publications have no citations, while eleven have only one citation, this could be attributed to the recent surge in research.

Table 3 Top 10 cited publications

S no	Author	Title	Year	Source	Citations	Reference
1	Zheng, Xiaoyan; Easa, Said M.; Yang, Zhengxian; Ji, Tao; Jiang, Zhenliang	Life-cycle sustainability assessment of pavement maintenance alternatives: Methodology and case study	2019	Journal of Cleaner Production	112	Zheng et al. 2019
2	Dong, Ya Hong; Ng, S. Thomas	A social life cycle assessment model for building construction in Hong Kong	2015	International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment	100	Dong and Ng 2015
3	Larsen, Vibeke Grupe; Tollin, Nicola; Sattrup, Peter Andreas; Birkved, Morten; Holmboe, Tine	What are the challenges in assessing circular economy for the built environment? A literature review on integrating LCA, LCC and S-LCA in life cycle sustainability assessment, LCSA	2022	Journal of Building Engineering	93	Larsen et al. 2022
4	Dong, Ya Hong; Ng, S. Thomas	A modeling framework to evaluate sustainability of building construction based on LCSA	2016	International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment	85	Dong and Ng 2016
5	Hossain, Md. Uzzal; Poon, Chi Sun; Dong, Ya Hong; Lo, Irene M. C.; Cheng, Jack C. P.	Development of social sustainability assessment method and a comparative case study on assessing recycled construction materials	2018	International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment	82	Hossain et al. 2018
6	Amini Toosi, Hashem; Lavagna, Monica; Leonforte, Fabrizio; Del Pero, Claudio; Aste, Niccolò	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment in Building Energy Retrofitting: A Review	2020	Sustainable Cities and Society	82	Amini Toosi et al. 2020
7	Liu, Siyu; Qian, Shunzhi	Evaluation of social life-cycle performance of buildings: Theoretical framework and impact assessment approach	2019	Journal of Cleaner Production	81	Liu and Qian 2019
8	Balasbaneh, Ali Tighnavard; Marsono, Abdul Kadir Bin; Khaleghi, Seyed Jalal	Sustainability choice of different hybrid timber structure for low medium cost single-story residential building: Environmental, economic and social assessment	2018	Journal of Building Engineering	74	Balasbaneh et al. 2018
9	Ferrari, Anna Maria; Volpi, Lucrezia; Pini, Martina ; Siligardi, Cristina; García-Muiña, Fernando Enrique ; Settembre-Blundo, Davide	Building a sustainability benchmarking framework of ceramic tiles based on life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA)	2019	Resources	63	Ferrari et al. 2019
10	Backes, Jana Gerta; Traverso, Marzia	Application of life cycle sustainability assessment in the construction sector: A systematic literature review	2021	Processes	61	Backes and Traverso 2021

4.5 Analysis by Keywords

This analysis involved two phases, firstly, the *indexed keywords* were analysed in VOSviewer, and then, *author keywords* were analysed. This analysis helps to highlight the linkages and current study interests as well as to indicate the limits of the research topic. This network helps to provide valuable insights in illustrating the themes which were concentrated in the selected publications (Escorcía Hernández *et al.* 2023). A study's keywords convey the core idea and topic of the research while summarising the contents of the research papers (Biswas *et al.* 2021).

Figure 5. Co-occurrence map of indexed keywords

4.5.1 Analysis of Indexed Keywords

For the indexed keywords, the red cluster is focused on *sustainable development and life cycle analysis* (Figure 5). The use of terms like *life cycle analysis*, *construction industry*, *sustainability*, *ecodesign* and *buildings* points towards the focus on environmental sustainability in construction. The green cluster (Figure 5) is focused on the *social and economic development pillar of sustainability*, emphasising their importance. These are important for decision-making while considering the economic and social impacts of the decisions on the people. Lastly, the blue cluster (Figure 5) encompasses *methodological and general academic themes*, featuring themes like *life cycle assessment*, *article*, *human* and *priority journal*, indicating the broad research of this cluster.

Life cycle and sustainable development are the biggest nodes and the most important keywords in the network. Strong connections with them elucidate the significance of the three pillars of sustainability - environmental, social and economic, and practical applications of life cycle thinking in the construction field.

4.5.2 Analysis of Author's Keywords

For the indexed keywords, the first cluster is red (Figure 6), which focuses on *life cycle thinking in construction* (both LCSA and S-LCA). S-LCA has the biggest nodes, symbolising most publications and the emphasis on social aspects in the field of sustainability. Also, S-LCA was used as a keyword in the Scopus search, so most publications will be focused on it. Circular economy which is also an important aspect of sustainability, is in this cluster, which indicates the reduction of waste and energy efficiency with full consideration of the social aspects. The second cluster is green (Figure 6), comprising LCA, LCC and sustainability, which are the two elements of LCSA, and to fulfil sustainability, these two methodologies are very important. This cluster focuses on environmental and economic pillars of

Figure 6. Co-occurrence map of author keywords

sustainability. This analysis suggests that researchers are increasingly recognising the interdependence of all the dimensions in construction sustainability rather than treating them in isolation.

4.6 Analysis by Bibliographic coupling of documents

In a bibliographic coupling network, the documents are featured by nodes that reference the same set of cited documents and the relationship between them is depicted by links (Escorcia Hernández *et al.* 2023). Two documents are said to be bibliographically coupled when they cite a common third document (Ma *et al.* 2022). The documents in the same cluster have a higher degree of bibliographic coupling, which means they have more shared references. It is crucial to observe that the bibliographic coupling of individual documents is possible to change over time, with the document numbering experiencing many alterations (Ma *et al.* 2022).

Figure 7. Bibliographic map of documents

In this analysis, a minimum of 20 citations per document in VOSviewer were chosen. The red cluster (Figure 7) is more focused on recent works, mainly on life cycle frameworks and integration of sustainability assessments in all three forms – social, environmental and economic. The blue cluster is mainly focused on real-world applications of S-LCA, here the main focus is *Hossain (2018)* (Figure 7). Green cluster mainly focuses on material sustainability (Figure 7). Yellow clusters have only two authors – Balasbaneh and Liu, with Liu having two publications in the same year. The last cluster with violet colour has one author with two publications in the same year, which seems disconnected from others but still connected. The strongest coupled papers are Backes (2021) and Dong (2016).

5 Conclusions and Further Research

5.1 Conclusion

The research findings indicate a clear increase in the volume of research in the field of Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) within the construction sector. Although S-LCA is a relatively new field of research, a sizable amount of research has already been performed. The geographical concentration of the research is still in the developed (western) part of the world, though there has been a significant increase in research in the East. Furthermore, co-authorship networks highlight research-sharing, which indicates a transfer of knowledge, thus bridging the gap between both research communities.

The highly cited papers emphasise on LCSA and S-LCA of the built environment, indicating the importance of the social pillar of sustainability in sustainable development. The analysis of the keywords reinforces the importance of economic, environmental and social impacts of construction, which is very important for sustainability, underscoring the importance of the above-mentioned methodologies in decision-making in construction.

This research will help the researchers evaluate past publications and understand the progress of the field. The documents found in this study and mentioned in the highest cited papers as well as in bibliographic coupling can be used by other researchers for their study as a background (reference), thus making their search easier. This will also help researchers in the field of S-LCA to understand the research in an aggregated dimension and analyse the different scholars working in this field.

Furthermore, bibliometric analysis is not a substitute for traditional review methods; rather they help to complement the reviews (Zupic and Čater 2015).

5.2 Limitations and Further Research

While the research gives valuable insights, it has a few limitations. Scopus has a vast quantity of peer-reviewed literature; future research can include Web of Science and Google Scholar to ensure a complete representation of scholarly literature. Moreover, VOSviewer is great for visualisations and research trends, but it is a black box, so further manual reviews are needed. Complementary software like CiteSpace or Bibliometrix with VOSviewer could help in result validation.

Given that S-LCA research is in its preliminary stages. The next phase of this research will involve a *three-phase systematic literature review* which will focus on the pillars of sustainability, methodologies, data typologies and thematic categories with emphasis on *Positive Energy Districts (PEDs) and affordable housing refurbishment*.

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